

The Role of AZT (Azidothymidine) in the Treatment of HIV and AIDS

Hasan Jasim Hami

Biology department, College of Science, University of Thi Qar, Thi Qar, Iraq

Ayam Al Anisi

Education Directorate of Thi-Qar, Ministry of Education, Iraq

Elahe Vadayekheiry

Research center for Animal Applied Biology, Mashhad Branch, Islamic Azad University, Mashhad, Iran

Amal F. Al-Gorani

Biology department, College of Science, University of Thi Qar, Thi Qar, Iraq

Jabbar Alrikaby

Biology department, College of Science, University of Thi Qar, Thi Qar, Iraq

Abstract

AIDS (Acquired Immune Deficiency Syndrome) is one of the threats to global health in the past several years, since the beginning, many study and research groups around the world are looking for effective methods and drugs in the treatment of this virus, currently there are a large number of drugs that have antiviral activity. They have been clinically evaluated. These drugs are divided into several groups based on their biological targets. Azidothymidine (AZT) is one of these drugs and is the first drug synthesized in the treatment of AIDS. In this article, we review the AZT drug in the treatment of AIDS.

Keywords: *AIDS treatment, antiretroviral activity, HIV lifecycle, immune suppression.*

Suggested citation: Hami, H.J., Al Anisi, A., Vadayekheiry, E., Al-Gorani, A.F., & Alrikaby, J. (2025). The Role of AZT (Azidothymidine) in the Treatment of HIV and AIDS. *European Journal of Ecology, Biology and Agriculture*, 2(3), 3-15. DOI: 10.59324/ejeba.2025.2(3).01

AIDS and Mechanism of Action

AIDS (Acquired Immune Deficiency Syndrome) refers to a collection of potentially fatal infections and diseases that arise when the immune system has been critically weakened by the HIV virus (Pennings, 2013).

Upon entering the body, the HIV virus targets T cells and initiates several steps, beginning with attachment or fusion. This initial phase of the HIV replication cycle involves the virus binding to the CD4 receptor on the target cell's surface through a specific interaction between the viral envelope glycoprotein, gp120, and the CD4 receptor. Additionally, gp41 associates with gp120, together forming the HIV spike trimers present on the surface of HIV particles (Dalglish, et al., 1984).

Scientists also discovered after further investigation that after binding to CD4 as the primary receptor, it must bind to the CCR5 or CNCR4 receptor in order to infect the cell. This process is called co-receptor binding. The virus selectively binds to a common receptor, this selective process is called tropism.

Depending on which central receptor a particular virus uses to initiate cell entry, patients' HIV infections are classified as either ccr5(r5) virus or x4 virus (Alkhatib, et al., 1996).

The binding of the virus to the CD4 target cell is the beginning of the HIV replication cycle process, which occurs through a specific interaction between the virus envelope glycoproteins called gp120 and the CD4 cell surface receptor.

Scientists also discovered after further investigation that after binding to CD4 as the primary receptor, it must bind to the CCR5 or CXCR4 receptor in order to infect the cell. This process is called co-receptor binding. The virus selectively binds to a co-receptor, this selective process is called tropism.

Depending on which co-receptor a particular virus uses to initiate cell entry, patients' HIV infections are classified as either ccr5(r5) virus or CXCR4 (x4) virus (Arts, & Hazuda, 2012).

Reverse Transcription

Reverse transcription refers to the mechanism by which RNA, carrying genetic information, is converted into DNA. Although RNA and DNA encode the same genetic instructions, they differ structurally: RNA typically exists as a single strand, while DNA is composed of two strands.

HIV carries out this transformation by releasing the enzyme reverse transcriptase (RT), enabling the viral genetic material to penetrate the nucleus of the CD4 cell.

Integration

After the viral RNA is transcribed into DNA, HIV introduces another enzyme, Integrase, into the CD4 cell's nucleus. This enzyme facilitates the integration of viral DNA into the DNA of the host CD4 cell.

Once the virus has replicated, it exits the host cell, and protease enzymes cleave the newly formed viral proteins, leading to the spread of infection. As a result, many therapeutic drugs are designed to target and disrupt various stages of this replication cycle.

Specifically, some drugs inhibit the virus during the entry stage by blocking the attachment or fusion process, targeting the glycoproteins gp120 or gp41, or the CD4 cell's primary or co-receptors, such as CCR5 or CXCR4 (Klatzmann, et al., 1984).

They can also exert their effect as RTI reverse transcriptase inhibitors, which are divided into two groups: nucleosides (NRTIs) and non-nucleosides (NNRTIs) (Craigie, & Bushman, 2012).

AIDS and AZT

A review of the history of AIDS shows that the disease was first recognized as a new clinical condition in 1981 (Arts, & Hazuda, 2012), even though individuals had been infected earlier. In 1983, Barré-Sinoussi and colleagues successfully isolated the retrovirus responsible for the disease, although a consensus had not yet been reached (Barré-Sinoussi, et al., 1983). The following year, Gallo managed to extract the virus from an AIDS patient, propagate it in a cell culture, and develop an antibody test, conclusively identifying the cause of AIDS (Gallo, et al., 1984). Shortly after AIDS was acknowledged as a novel disease, research into possible treatments began at the National Cancer Institute (NCI). At the time, the prevailing belief was that retroviruses, due to their ability to integrate into host cell DNA as proviruses, were untreatable using antiviral therapies (Harden, 2012).

While antimicrobial drugs were already well-developed, there was limited progress in antiviral treatments, with acyclovir—the anti-herpes medication approved in 1982—being one of the few antivirals in clinical use. Although HIV appeared simpler than herpes viruses, containing only nine genes, it presented unique therapeutic challenges.

Additionally, although HIV infected a relatively small number of T cells, widespread T cell dysfunction was observed, implying that the damage was secondary and indirect, and could not be reversed merely by halting HIV replication. This raised serious concerns about the prospects of effective AIDS treatment.

Nonetheless, observations from bone marrow transplants suggested that the immune system could regenerate within months under appropriate conditions. Based on this, researchers hypothesized that stopping HIV replication might stabilize and even restore the immune system within a short period (Frank, et al., 1987).

Given this hypothesis, scientists focused their efforts on targeting the reverse transcriptase enzyme, which is essential for retrovirus and hepadnavirus replication but absent in eukaryotic cells. Previous work on human T-cell leukemia virus type I (HTLV-1) had provided the basis for designing assays to assess antiviral drug efficacy (Mitsuya, & Broder, 1987).

The research team initially tested suramin. Although early laboratory results appeared promising, subsequent clinical trials revealed no significant clinical benefit or reversal of HIV-induced immune suppression. Consequently, attention shifted to AZT (De Clercq, 1979; Broder, et al., 1985).

Azidothymidine (AZT) had originally been synthesized by Jerome Horwitz in 1964 for potential cancer treatment. Laboratory testing confirmed its strong anti-HIV activity (Horwitz, Chua, & Noel, 1964), leading to its rapid progression into clinical trials, with the first administration to an AIDS patient in July 1985 (Mitsuya, et al., 1985).

At that time, real-time PCR technology to measure viral load had not yet been developed, so researchers relied on immunological and clinical indicators to assess AZT's effectiveness. While some scientists questioned whether increased CD4 counts truly indicated therapeutic success, researchers at Burroughs Wellcome emphasized results from controlled, placebo-based clinical trials.

One such trial involved 282 patients across 12 centers in the United States: 147 received AZT, and 135 received a placebo. The study demonstrated that 19 patients in the placebo group died compared to only one death among the AZT group, showing a striking difference. Side effects included bone marrow suppression, nausea, muscle pain, insomnia, and headaches (Fischl, et al., 1990; Richman, et al., 1987).

Despite this major step forward, skepticism persisted. Some continued to deny that HIV was the cause of AIDS, attributing the disease to the use of drugs such as AZT itself. Such misconceptions, notably endorsed by the South African government, tragically resulted in many preventable deaths (Specter, 2007).

Ultimately, after approximately 25 months of laboratory research and clinical evaluation, AZT gained regulatory approval in March 1987 following phase II clinical studies (Yarchoan, & Broder, 1989).

AZT Mechanism of Action

The antiviral mechanism of AZT primarily involves blocking the activity of reverse transcriptase (RT), a crucial HIV enzyme responsible for synthesizing proviral DNA. HIV reverse transcriptase is a specialized DNA polymerase capable of using viral RNA as a template to create double-stranded DNA, which then integrates into the genome of the host cell. AZT became the first recognized nucleoside reverse transcriptase inhibitor (NRTI) (Kohlstaedt, et al., 1992).

Structurally, AZT is a thymidine analog, distinguished by the substitution of an azido group for the hydroxyl group. Similar to other NRTIs, its active triphosphate form is generated within cells through phosphorylation by kinases at the 5'-OH position.

Originally, AZT was utilized in the treatment of human lymphomas and infections caused by other mammalian retroviruses. Studies further demonstrated that AZT could alleviate neurological complications related to AIDS, such as peripheral neuropathy and dementia.

Currently, the FDA has approved seven nucleosides and one nucleotide for HIV treatment: didanosine (ddI), zalcitabine (ddC), stavudine (d4T), lamivudine (3TC), abacavir (ABC), tenofovir disoproxil fumarate (TDF; an oral prodrug of tenofovir [TFV]), and emtricitabine (FTC), which received approval in 2003 (Maeda, et al., 2019).

NRTIs are initially pharmacologically inactive and must undergo sequential phosphorylation by host kinases and phosphotransferases to form deoxynucleoside triphosphate (dNTP) analogs that actively inhibit viral replication. In their triphosphate forms, these compounds act as chain terminators for viral reverse transcriptase enzymes (Mehellou, & De Clercq, 2010).

By competitively binding to the reverse transcriptase enzyme, the triphosphate forms of NRTIs are incorporated into the growing DNA chain, prematurely halting viral replication. When viral DNA synthesis is disrupted in this way, the incomplete genome can subsequently be degraded by cellular enzymes.

For activation, NRTIs must first enter host cells, typically via passive diffusion or carrier-mediated transport mechanisms. Over 350 transporters from the solute carrier (SLC) family are capable of transporting NRTIs. Multidrug resistance-associated protein 4 (MRP4) and related transporters mediate the efflux of monophosphate forms, while unphosphorylated nucleosides are handled by ATP-binding cassette (ABC) family transporters such as breast cancer resistance protein and P-glycoprotein. Furthermore, monophosphate metabolites are excreted renally via specific transporters (Jorajuria, et al., 2004).

The initial phosphorylation of NRTIs is catalyzed by four main deoxynucleoside kinases, including cytosolic deoxycytidine kinase (dCK), thymidine kinase 1 (TK1), and mitochondrial enzymes such as deoxyguanosine kinase and thymidine kinase 2, which are responsible for salvaging endogenous nucleosides (Arnér, & Eriksson, 1995).

Subsequently, nucleoside monophosphate (NMP) kinases such as thymidylate kinase, uridylate-cytidylate kinase, and adenylate kinases 1–5, along with guanylate kinase, add the second phosphate group.

Finally, enzymes like phosphoglycerate kinase, pyruvate kinase, and creatine kinase catalyze the addition of the third phosphate group, completing the formation of the triphosphate active form (Bourdaï, 1996).

While some NRTIs, such as ddC, 3TC, FTC, and TFV, are excreted unchanged via urine, others, including AZT, undergo metabolism. AZT is processed by the cytochrome P450 system, resulting in a metabolite containing a partially modified amine group (Ray, & Hitchcock, 2014).

Additionally, AZT participates in broader catabolic pathways; it is converted to 5'-O-glucuronide through the action of UDP-glucuronosyltransferase (UGT), leading to the excretion of approximately 74% of the administered dose in urine as 5'-O-glucuronide (McDowell, et al., 1999).

In their triphosphate forms, NRTIs compete with natural dNTPs for incorporation into HIV reverse transcriptase. The structural variety of NRTIs ensures that their triphosphates can effectively challenge dNTPs for binding at the enzyme's active site.

HIV reverse transcriptase itself is a heterodimer composed of two subunits, p66 and p51, with p66 exhibiting DNA polymerase and RNase H activities (Ibbotson, & Perry, 2003).

Today, NRTIs form a core component of antiretroviral therapy, typically used in combination regimens with other NRTIs or non-nucleoside reverse transcriptase inhibitors (NNRTIs) to create highly active antiretroviral therapy (HAART) protocols (Pozniak, et al., 2006).

NNRTIs, unlike NRTIs, are small molecules that inhibit reverse transcriptase by inducing structural distortions at the enzyme's active site, thereby preventing the proper incorporation of incoming dNTPs (Steitz, 1999).

Fixed Dose Combinations (FDCs)

An important issue in the use of AZT, like other NRTIs, is their toxicity, which causes side effects such as diarrhea, headache, bone marrow suppression, nausea and vomiting.

Therefore, pharmacists and chemists have been looking for more effective compounds to improve AZT effective.

The combined approach of medicine or polypharmacology is very popular in the treatment of AIDS today, although it should be noted that there is no vaccine or medicine for definitive treatment of AIDS, but polypharmacology has been able to improve the quality of life of patients and turn AIDS into a chronic disease. Make it controllable so that it does not spread.

Research has shown that drug combinations have less drug resistance because the administration of two drugs that have different functions can reduce the chance of mutation.

few fixed dose combinations (FDCs) AND multi-target-directed ligands (MTDLs) ARE THE METHOD FOR aids TREATMENT

A few fixed dose combinations (FDCs), have also been developed, for example the combination AZT/ABC/3TC With the name (Trizivir), TDF/FTC combination (Truvada), AZT/3TC combination (Combivir), and ABC/3TC (Epzicom). Also, drugs with NNRT combination are being developed and investigated, such as the combination of TDF/FTC and NNRT Iefavirenz named (Atripla) and d4T/3TC and the NNRTI nevirapine.

Among them, Camovir and Trizivir contain AZT:

Camovir

Camovir became the first fixed-dose combination therapy approved by the FDA in 1997, following the earlier introduction of AZT as the first medication for AIDS treatment. This combination included four other NRTIs, among them lamivudine (3TC), which soon became widely available (Ibbotson, & Perry, 2003).

Neuropathy emerged as a significant concern in the search for effective anti-AIDS drugs. During the late 1990s and early 2000s, stavudine and lamivudine were among the most commonly prescribed treatments. However, the development of lactic acidosis and hepatic steatosis as side effects eventually led to a decline in their use (Carr, et al., 2000).

Research demonstrated that combining AZT with 3TC helped reduce the virus's resistance to treatment. Furthermore, studies indicated that 3TC was less toxic than AZT, with headache and insomnia being its primary adverse effects. Continued clinical investigations revealed that adding 3TC to AZT monotherapy produced significantly better outcomes compared to AZT alone (Portsmouth, & Scott, 2022).

The dual therapy consisted of two NRTIs: azidothymidine (also known as zidovudine, 3'-Azido-3'-deoxythymidine, AZT), a thymidine analog, and lamivudine (2'-Deoxy-3'-thiacytidine, 3TC; GlaxoSmithKline Ltd, Brentford Middlesex, UK), a cytosine analog. Each Combivir tablet delivers 300 mg of AZT and 150 mg of lamivudine, administered twice daily (Portsmouth, & Scott, 2022).

Both lamivudine and zidovudine are nucleoside analogs with potent activity against HIV, and lamivudine also exhibits efficacy against the hepatitis B virus (HBV). Like other NRTIs, these drugs require

intracellular phosphorylation to their active triphosphate forms. Their primary mechanism involves terminating the viral DNA chain during reverse transcription. In vitro studies have shown that lamivudine-TP and zidovudine-TP selectively inhibit HIV-1 and HIV-2 replication. Additionally, lamivudine retains antiviral activity against HIV strains resistant to zidovudine. Resistance to lamivudine typically results from the M184V mutation, which occurs near the reverse transcriptase's active site. This mutation reduces viral sensitivity to lamivudine and impairs viral replication, and has been observed both in vitro and in clinical settings where lamivudine-containing regimens are used (Pluda, et al., 1995).

Clinical trials have confirmed that combining lamivudine with zidovudine significantly decreases HIV-1 viral loads while increasing CD4+ T-cell counts. Data from these studies demonstrate that this combination therapy meaningfully reduces the risk of disease progression and mortality (Katzenstein, et al., 2000).

Lamivudine and zidovudine are frequently included in combination antiretroviral regimens, either alongside other NRTIs or drugs from different classes, such as protease inhibitors (PIs) or non-nucleoside reverse transcriptase inhibitors (NNRTIs).

Moreover, treatment strategies involving lamivudine have proven effective both in patients newly starting antiretroviral therapy and in those harboring HIV strains with the M184V mutation. Clinical evidence also suggests that lamivudine combined with zidovudine delays the emergence of zidovudine-resistant HIV isolates in patients without prior antiretroviral exposure (Gulick, et al., 2004).

Both drugs are absorbed through the gastrointestinal tract. The oral bioavailability of zidovudine in adults ranges between 60% and 70%, while lamivudine's bioavailability is slightly higher, between 80% and 85% (Amarenco, et al., 2011).

Trizivir

Another notable medication is the Trizivir tablet, which combines three nucleoside analogs: 300 mg of zidovudine, 300 mg of abacavir—a synthetic carbocyclic nucleoside analog ((1S, cis)-4-[2-amino-6-(cyclopropylamino)-9H-purin-9-yl]-2-cyclopentene-1-methanol sulfate)—and 150 mg of lamivudine ((2R,cis)-4-amino-1-(2-hydroxymethyl-1,3-oxathiolan-5-yl)-(1H)-pyrimidin-2-one), the (-) enantiomer of a cytidine dideoxy analog. In addition to these active components, each tablet also contains excipients such as sodium starch glycolate, magnesium stearate, and microcrystalline cellulose. Trizivir is formulated for administration twice daily (Adams, 1996).

Trizivir holds a significant place in HIV therapy owing to its strong antiviral activity and the convenience of its dosing regimen, whether used alone or in combination with other treatments. Moreover, it has been found to mitigate hyperlipidemia, a common adverse effect associated with antiretroviral therapy, although allergic reactions have been observed in a small subset of patients (International Tribunal for the Law of the Sea, 2020).

Abacavir, lamivudine, and zidovudine are all members of the nucleoside reverse transcriptase inhibitor (NRTI) class, functioning through conversion into active 5'-triphosphate metabolites. The triphosphate forms of these drugs inhibit HIV-1 reverse transcriptase by incorporating into viral DNA and terminating its elongation (Ibbotson, & Perry, 2003).

Experimental data demonstrated that lamivudine does not exhibit antagonistic interactions when used with other antiviral agents. Similarly, zidovudine maintains its efficacy when combined with other antivirals. Abacavir's antiviral activity also remains uncompromised when used alongside NRTIs, NNRTIs, or protease inhibitors (PIs) in cell culture studies (Adams, 1996).

Resistance of HIV-1 to lamivudine primarily arises through amino acid substitutions, either M184I or more commonly M184V, occurring near the enzyme's active site. Specific genotypic alterations, including

mutations at codons M184V, K65R, L74V, and Y115F within the reverse transcriptase gene, result in a clinically significant elevation of the EC₅₀ compared to wild-type strains (Keiser, & Nassar, 2007).

All three active ingredients in Trizivir—abacavir, lamivudine, and zidovudine—are rapidly and efficiently absorbed through the gastrointestinal tract. In adults, the absolute oral bioavailability is approximately 60–70% for abacavir, 80–85% for lamivudine, and about 83% for zidovudine (Ibbotson, & Perry, 2003).

Multi-Target-Directed Ligands (MTDLs)

Today, MTDL is used as a new option in the treatment of multifactorial diseases. The advantage of using these single molecules is less drug interactions due to the number of pills, facilitating treatment compliance, predictable pharmacokinetics and better patient tolerance. Mtdl are divided into two categories, co-drug and hybrid drugs (Amarenco, et al., 2011).

Hybrid Drugs

Hybrid drugs are compounds that integrate two or more pharmacophores with established biological activity into a single molecular structure. In concomitant drug systems, two active agents are chemically connected via a covalent bond, with each molecule acting as a carrier for the other, resulting in synergistic effects that become active in the presence of one another.

Chemically, hybrid molecules can be classified into three types: linked, fused, and merged hybrids. Fused and merged hybrids do not contain a distinct bond between components, whereas linked hybrids involve either a direct connection or a shared structural element between the pharmacophores.

AZT-based hybrids have shown potential as potent agents capable of targeting multiple phases of the HIV-1 replication cycle.

The research team led by Karamasa was the first to explore and synthesize AZT-based hybrids, creating a combination of a thymine ring and an NNRTI moiety connected via a methylene linker. Following this, they developed further hybrids by combining AZT and TSAO-T frameworks using various spacer groups and sugar modifications (Velázquez, et al., 1995).

Pontikis also contributed to this field by synthesizing grafted hybrids containing both an NRTI and an NNRTI. Among these, hybrids formed from AZT and HEPT analogs demonstrated superior anti-HIV properties (Pontikis, et al., 2000).

Subsequent studies focused on natural product derivatives, offering valuable leads for hybrid drug development. Betulin, a natural product known for diverse biological activities, was chemically modified to inhibit HIV maturation and viral entry by targeting gp-120 (Li, et al., 2006).

Later, Xiong and colleagues synthesized fourteen novel hybrids by combining AZT with betulin derivatives. They discovered that employing a 2,2-dimethylsuccinyl spacer between the C-28 position of the triterpene scaffold and AZT provided the most effective linker (Xiong, et al., 2010).

Additionally, the azido group of AZT was utilized to form triazoles through click chemistry with terminal alkynes, leading to a series of triazole derivatives based on AZT and betulinic acid. These derivatives were found to inhibit key HIV-1 enzymes such as reverse transcriptase, integrase, and protease (Feng, et al., 2021).

Further, a hybrid of AZT and isatin was created using a 1,2,3-triazole linkage.

Aminiak and his team developed multitarget hybrids aimed at treating HIV and malaria coinfections by linking AZT with either dihydroartemisinin (DHA) or chloroquine (CQ), two known antimalarial scaffolds (Aminake, et al., 2012).

In another approach, Senthil Kumar and collaborators engineered dual-action hybrids targeting HIV and tuberculosis by attaching AZT's C-50 hydroxyl group to anti-mycobacterial fluoroquinolones. In vitro assessments showed that these hybrids exhibited greater cytotoxicity compared to AZT alone (Senthilkumar, et al., 2009).

Co-Drugs

AZT-based hybrids are capable of producing highly active compounds that can interfere with various stages of the HIV-1 lifecycle. Thanks to its enhanced cellular uptake, AZT serves as an excellent scaffold for designing combination agents.

In 1988, Bosso and his team synthesized both homo- and heterodimeric nucleotides, demonstrating that dimers linked through a phosphate bridge offered greater anti-HIV efficacy than monomeric forms (Busso, et al., 1988).

Ejichi developed nucleotide heterodimers evaluated for their ability to inhibit HIV-1, including resistant variants. These heterodimers combined either AZT or DDI with a modified uracil derivative, and it was found that AZT-containing compounds exhibited superior antiviral potency, greater cell protection, and better inhibition than AZT alone (Ijichi, et al., 1996).

McGuigan and colleagues designed symmetric (5',5')-phosphotriester dimers of AZT. Their findings showed that AZT derivatives retained anti-HIV-1 activity, with the 2,2,2-trifluoroethyl-containing compound displaying the strongest viral inhibition and cell protection. Nevertheless, comparative analyses indicated that these dimers were less active than AZT alone, suggesting a potential role as intracellular reservoirs for the free drug (McGuigan, et al., 1993).

Another research group synthesized homo- and heterodimers of AZT and stavudine (d4T) using carbonate and carbamate linkers. All carbonate-linked compounds were active against HIV, whereas carbamate-linked molecules exhibited weaker antiviral effects, likely due to faster chemical and enzymatic hydrolysis, releasing the active AZT (Taourirte, et al., 2004).

Finally, Matsumoto and colleagues sought to enhance antiviral potency and membrane permeability by combining a protease inhibitor (either KNI-413 or KNI-272) with AZT via an ester bond. Their hybrids demonstrated significantly stronger anti-HIV activity compared to the parent compounds alone (Matsumoto, et al., 2001).

Conclusions

Millions of people around the world are affected by AIDS, but today, with drugs, the mortality rate has decreased, the quality of life of patients has improved, and it is known as a controllable chronic disease. 1987 was a turning point in the history of AIDS with the arrival of AZT as the first drug

Since then, other drugs have entered the treatment cycle, but despite the side effects and viral resistance, it is necessary to search for new and stronger drugs and methods with less side effects.

In summary, this review analyzes the antiretroviral activity of drugs and molecules containing the AZT scaffold.

References

Adams, J. (1996). Drug evaluation: Abacavir. *Australian Prescriber*, 19(1), 5–7. <https://doi.org/10.18773/austprescr.1996.007>

- Alkhatib, G., Combadiere, C., Broder, C. C., Feng, Y., Kennedy, P. E., Murphy, P. M., & Berger, E. A. (1996). CC CKR5: A RANTES, MIP-1 α , MIP-1 β receptor as a fusion cofactor for macrophage-tropic HIV-1. *Science*, 272(5270), 1955–1958. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.272.5270.1955>
- Amarenco, P., Bogousslavsky, J., Callahan, A. 3rd, Goldstein, L. B., Hennerici, M., Rudolph, A. E., Silleisen, H., Simunovic, L., Szarek, M., Welch, K. M. A., & Zivin, J. A. (2011). High-dose atorvastatin after stroke or transient ischemic attack. *The New England Journal of Medicine*, 365(8), 687–696. <https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJMoa1104271>
- Aminake, M. N., Mahajan, A., Kumar, V., Hans, R., Wiesner, L., Taylor, D., Addai-Mensah, O., & Becker, K. (2012). Synthesis and evaluation of hybrid drugs for a potential HIV/AIDS-malaria combination therapy. *Bioorganic & Medicinal Chemistry*, 20(17), 5277–5289. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bmc.2012.07.034>
- Arnér, E. S. J., & Eriksson, S. (1995). Mammalian deoxyribonucleoside kinases. *Pharmacology & Therapeutics*, 67(2), 155–186. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0163-7258\(95\)00011-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/0163-7258(95)00011-9)
- Arts, E. J., & Hazuda, D. J. (2012). HIV-1 antiretroviral drug therapy. *Cold Spring Harbor Perspectives in Medicine*, 2(4), a007161. <https://doi.org/10.1101/cshperspect.a007161>
- Barré-Sinoussi, F., Chermann, J. C., Rey, F., Nugeyre, M. T., Chamaret, S., Gruest, J., Dautuet, C., Axler-Blin, C., Vézinet-Brun, F., Rouzioux, C., Rozenbaum, W., & Montagnier, L. (1983). Isolation of a T-lymphotropic retrovirus from a patient at risk for acquired immune deficiency syndrome (AIDS). *Science*, 220(4599), 868–871. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.6189183>
- Bourdais, J., Biondi, R., Sarfati, S., Guerreiro, C., Lascu, I., Janin, J., & Delepierre, M. (1996). Cellular phosphorylation of anti-HIV nucleosides: Role of nucleoside diphosphate kinase. *Journal of Biological Chemistry*, 271(14), 7887–7890. <https://doi.org/10.1074/jbc.271.14.7887>
- Broder, S., Collins, J. M., Markham, P. D., Redfield, R. R., Hoth, D. F., Groopman, J. E., Blick, M., Gelmann, E. P., & Gallo, R. C. (1985). Effects of suramin on HTLV-III/LAV infection presenting as Kaposi's sarcoma or AIDS-related complex: Clinical pharmacology and suppression of virus replication in vivo. *The Lancet*, 326(8456), 627–630. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(85\)90002-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(85)90002-9)
- Busso, M., Mian, A. M., Hahn, E. F., & Resnick, L. (1988). Nucleotide dimers suppress HIV expression in vitro. *AIDS Research and Human Retroviruses*, 4(6), 449–455. <https://doi.org/10.1089/aid.1988.4.449>
- Carr, A., Miller, J., Matthew, L., & Cooper, D. A. (2000). A syndrome of lipoatrophy, lactic acidemia and liver dysfunction associated with HIV nucleoside analogue therapy: Contribution to protease inhibitor-related lipodystrophy syndrome. *AIDS*, 14(3), F25–F32.
- Craigie, R., & Bushman, F. D. (2012). HIV DNA integration. *Cold Spring Harbor Perspectives in Medicine*, 2(7), a006890. <https://doi.org/10.1101/cshperspect.a006890>
- Dalgleish, A. G., Clapham, P. R., Crawford, D. H., Greaves, M. F., Weiss, R. A., Beverley, P. C., Kinnon, C., & Lanchbury, J. S. (1984). The CD4 (T4) antigen is an essential component of the receptor for the AIDS retrovirus. *Nature*, 312(5996), 763–767. <https://doi.org/10.1038/312763a0>
- De Clercq, E. (1979). Suramin: A potent inhibitor of the reverse transcriptase of RNA tumor viruses. *Cancer Letters*, 8(1), 9–22. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0304-3835\(79\)90101-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/0304-3835(79)90101-3)
- Feng, L. S., Zheng, M. J., Zhao, F., & Liu, D. (2021). 1,2,3-Triazole hybrids with anti-HIV-1 activity. *Archiv der Pharmazie*, 354(1), 2000163. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ardp.202000163>
- Fischl, M. A., Richman, D. D., Grieco, M. H., Gottlieb, M. S., Volberding, P. A., Laskin, O. L., Leedom, J. M., Groopman, J. E., Mildvan, D., Schooley, R. T., Jackson, G. G., Durack, D. T., & King, D. (1990). The safety and efficacy of zidovudine (AZT) in the treatment of subjects with mildly symptomatic human

- immunodeficiency virus type 1 (HIV) infection. *Annals of Internal Medicine*, 112(10), 727–737. <https://doi.org/10.7326/0003-4819-112-10-727>
- Frank, K. B., McKernan, P. A., Smith, R. A., & Smece, D. F. (1987). Visna virus as an in vitro model for human immunodeficiency virus and inhibition by ribavirin, phosphonoformate, and 2',3'-dideoxynucleosides. *Antimicrobial Agents and Chemotherapy*, 31(9), 1369–1374. <https://doi.org/10.1128/AAC.31.9.1369>
- Gallo, R. C., Salahuddin, S. Z., Popovic, M., Shearer, G. M., Kaplan, M., Haynes, B. F., Palker, T. J., Redfield, R., Oleske, J., Safai, B., White, G., Foster, P., & Markham, P. D. (1984). Frequent detection and isolation of cytopathic retroviruses (HTLV-III) from patients with AIDS and at risk for AIDS. *Science*, 224(4648), 500–503. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.6200936>
- Gulick, R. M., Ribaud, H. J., Shikuma, C. M., Lustgarten, S., Squires, K. E., Meyer, W. A., Acosta, E. P., Schackman, B. R., Pilcher, C. D., Murphy, R. L., & Adults AIDS Clinical Trials Group Study A5095 Team. (2004). Triple-nucleoside regimens versus efavirenz-containing regimens for the initial treatment of HIV-1 infection. *The New England Journal of Medicine*, 350(18), 1850–1861. <https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJMoa032282>
- Harden, V. A. (2012). *AIDS at 30: A history*. Potomac Books. <https://www.amazon.com/AIDS-at-30-Victoria-Harden/dp/1597972940>
- Horwitz, J. P., Chua, J., & Noel, M. (1964). Nucleosides. V. The monomesylates of 1-(2'-deoxy-β-D-lyxofuranosyl)thymine. *The Journal of Organic Chemistry*, 29(7), 2076–2078. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jo01030a546>
- Ibbotson, T., & Perry, C. M. (2003). Lamivudine/zidovudine/abacavir: Triple combination tablet. *Drugs*, 63(11), 1089–1098. <https://doi.org/10.2165/00003495-200363110-00004>
- Ijichi, K., Fujiwara, M., Mori, K., Morozumi, M., Machida, H., & Shigeta, S. (1996). Antiviral activities of nucleotide heterodimers against human immunodeficiency virus type 1 in vitro. *Antiviral Research*, 31(1–2), 115–120. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0166-3542\(96\)01051-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/0166-3542(96)01051-5)
- International Tribunal for the Law of the Sea. (2020). Annex I. *Yearbook of the International Tribunal for the Law of the Sea*, 23, 193–214. https://doi.org/10.1163/9789004470363_011
- Jorajuria, S., Dereuddre-Bosquet, N., Naissant-Storck, K., Dormont, D., & Clayette, P. (2004). Differential expression levels of MRP1, MRP4, and MRP5 in response to human immunodeficiency virus infection in human macrophages. *Antimicrobial Agents and Chemotherapy*, 48(5), 1889–1891. <https://doi.org/10.1128/AAC.48.5.1889-1891.2004>
- Katzenstein, D. A., Hughes, M., Albrecht, M., Hammer, S., Para, M., Murphy, R., Valentine, F., Cherng, D., Bassiakos, Y., & Hirsch, M. (2000). Virologic and CD4+ cell responses to new nucleoside regimens: Switching to stavudine or adding lamivudine after prolonged zidovudine treatment of human immunodeficiency virus infection. ACTG 302 Study Team. *AIDS Research and Human Retroviruses*, 16(11), 1031–1037. <https://doi.org/10.1089/08892220050058570>
- Keiser, P., & Nassar, N. (2007). Abacavir sulfate/lamivudine/zidovudine fixed combination in the treatment of HIV infection. *Expert Opinion on Pharmacotherapy*, 8(4), 477–483. <https://doi.org/10.1517/14656566.8.4.477>
- Klatzmann, D., Champagne, E., Chamaret, S., Gruest, J., Guetard, D., Hercend, T., Gluckman, J. C., & Montagnier, L. (1984). T-lymphocyte T4 molecule behaves as the receptor for human retrovirus LAV. *Nature*, 312(5996), 767–768. <https://doi.org/10.1038/312767a0>

- Kohlstaedt, L. A., Wang, J., Friedman, J. M., Rice, P. A., & Steitz, T. A. (1992). Crystal structure at 3.5 Å resolution of HIV-1 reverse transcriptase complexed with an inhibitor. *Science*, 256(5065), 1783–1790. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1377403>
- Li, F., Zoumplis, D., Matallana, C., Kilgore, N. R., Reddick, M., Yunus, A. S., Ptak, R. G., & Parniak, M. A. (2006). Determinants of activity of the HIV-1 maturation inhibitor PA-457. *Virology*, 356(1–2), 217–224. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.virol.2006.08.027>
- Maeda, K., Das, D., Kobayakawa, T., Tamamura, H., & Takeuchi, H. (2019). Discovery and development of anti-HIV therapeutic agents: Progress towards improved HIV medication. *Current Topics in Medicinal Chemistry*, 19(18), 1621–1649. <https://doi.org/10.2174/1568026619666190507103602>
- Matsumoto, H., Matsuda, T., Nakata, S., Mitoguchi, T., Kimura, T., Hayashi, Y., & Baba, M. (2001). Synthesis and biological evaluation of prodrug-type anti-HIV agents: Ester conjugates of carboxylic acid-containing dipeptide HIV protease inhibitors and a reverse transcriptase inhibitor. *Bioorganic & Medicinal Chemistry*, 9(2), 417–430. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0968-0896\(00\)00253-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0968-0896(00)00253-5)
- McDowell, J. A., Chittick, G. E., Ravitch, J. R., Polk, R. E., Kerkering, T. M., & Stein, D. S. (1999). Pharmacokinetics of [¹⁴C]abacavir, a human immunodeficiency virus type 1 (HIV-1) reverse transcriptase inhibitor, administered in a single oral dose to HIV-1-infected adults: A mass balance study. *Antimicrobial Agents and Chemotherapy*, 43(12), 2855–2861. <https://doi.org/10.1128/AAC.43.12.2855>
- McGuigan, C., Pathirana, R. N., Balzarini, J., & De Clercq, E. (1993). Intracellular delivery of bioactive AZT nucleotides by aryl phosphate derivatives of AZT. *Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*, 36(8), 1048–1052. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jm00059a007>
- Mehellou, Y., & De Clercq, E. (2010). Twenty-six years of anti-HIV drug discovery: Where do we stand and where do we go? *Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*, 53(2), 521–538. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jm900492g>
- Mitsuya, H., & Broder, S. (1987). Strategies for antiviral therapy in AIDS. *Nature*, 325(6107), 773–778. <https://doi.org/10.1038/325773a0>
- Mitsuya, H., Weinhold, K. J., Furman, P. A., St Clair, M. H., Lehrman, S. N., Gallo, R. C., Bolognesi, D., & Broder, S. (1985). 3'-Azido-3'-deoxythymidine (BW A509U): An antiviral agent that inhibits the infectivity and cytopathic effect of human T-lymphotropic virus type III/lymphadenopathy-associated virus in vitro. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 82(20), 7096–7100. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.82.20.7096>
- Patients with human immunodeficiency virus infection and prior antiretroviral therapy. (2012).
- Pennings, P. S. (2013). HIV drug resistance: Problems and perspectives. *Infectious Disease Reports*, 5(Suppl. 1), 21–25. <https://doi.org/10.4081/idr.2013.s1.e5>
- Pluda, J. M., Cooley, T. P., Montaner, J. S. G., Sanden, G., Shay, L. E., Reinhalter, N. E., Helman, L. J., Grochow, L., & Yarchoan, R. (1995). A Phase I/II study of 2'-Deoxy-3'-Thiacytidine (Lamivudine) in patients with advanced human immunodeficiency virus infection. *The Journal of Infectious Diseases*, 171(6), 1438–1447. <https://doi.org/10.1093/infdis/171.6.1438>
- Pontikis, R., Dollé, V., Guillaumel, J., Dechaux, E., Note, R., Nguyen, C. H., & Aubertin, A. M. (2000). Synthesis and evaluation of “AZT-HEPT”, “AZT-pyridinone”, and “ddC-HEPT” conjugates as inhibitors of HIV reverse transcriptase. *Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*, 43(10), 1927–1939. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jm991125l>
- Portsmouth, S. D., & Scott, C. J. (2022). The renaissance of fixed dose combinations: Combivir. *Therapeutics and Clinical Risk Management*, 18, 279–290. <https://doi.org/10.2147/TCRM.S346724>

- Pozniak, A. L., Gallant, J. E., DeJesus, E., Arribas, J. R., Gazzard, B., Campo, R. E., Lu, B., McColl, D., Chuck, S. L., & Enejosa, J. V. (2006). Tenofovir disoproxil fumarate, emtricitabine, and efavirenz versus fixed-dose zidovudine/lamivudine and efavirenz in antiretroviral-naïve patients: Virologic, immunologic, and morphologic changes—a 96-week analysis. *Journal of Acquired Immune Deficiency Syndromes*, 43(5), 535–540. <https://doi.org/10.1097/01.qai.0000243099.23346.46>
- Ray, A. S., & Hitchcock, M. J. M. (2014). Metabolism of antiviral nucleosides and nucleotides. In *Antiviral Strategies* (pp. 301–315). American Society for Microbiology. <https://doi.org/10.1128/9781555815493.ch17>
- Richman, D. D., Fischl, M. A., Grieco, M. H., Gottlieb, M. S., Volberding, P. A., Laskin, O. L., Leedom, J. M., Groopman, J. E., Mildvan, D., Schooley, R. T., Jackson, G. G., Durack, D. T., & King, D. (1987). The toxicity of azidothymidine (AZT) in the treatment of patients with AIDS and AIDS-related complex. *The New England Journal of Medicine*, 317(4), 192–197. <https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJM198707233170402>
- Senthilkumar, P., Long, J., Swetha, R., Shruthi, V., Wang, R. R., Preethi, S., & Chen, C. H. (2009). Synthesis of Zidovudine derivatives with anti-HIV-1 and antibacterial activities. *Nucleosides, Nucleotides and Nucleic Acids*, 28(8), 719–734. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15257770902736442>
- Specter, M. (2007, March 12). The denialists: The dangerous attacks on the consensus about HIV and AIDS. *The New Yorker*, 32–38. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/17342872/>
- Steitz, T. A. (1999). DNA polymerases: Structural diversity and common mechanisms. *Journal of Biological Chemistry*, 274(25), 17395–17398. <https://doi.org/10.1074/jbc.274.25.17395>
- Taourirte, M., Ait Mohamed, L., Rochdi, A., Vasseur, J. J., Fernández, S., Ferrero, M., & Morvan, F. (2004). Chemoenzymatic syntheses of homo- and heterodimers of AZT and d4T, and evaluation of their anti-HIV activity. *Nucleosides, Nucleotides and Nucleic Acids*, 23(4–5), 701–714. <https://doi.org/10.1081/NCN-120037749>
- Velázquez, S., Alvarez, R., San-Félix, A., Jimeno, M. L., De Clercq, E., Balzarini, J., & Camarasa, M. J. (1995). Synthesis and anti-HIV activity of [AZT]-[TSAO-T] and [AZT]-[HEPT] dimers as potential multifunctional inhibitors of HIV-1 reverse transcriptase. *Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*, 38(10), 1641–1649. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jm00010a008>
- Xiong, J., Kashiwada, Y., Chen, C. H., Qian, K., Morris-Natschke, S. L., Lee, K. H., & Yang, S. (2010). Conjugates of betulin derivatives with AZT as potent anti-HIV agents. *Bioorganic & Medicinal Chemistry*, 18(17), 6451–6469. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bmc.2010.06.062>
- Yarchoan, R., & Broder, S. (1989). Anti-retroviral therapy of AIDS and related disorders: General principles and specific development of dideoxynucleosides. *Pharmacology & Therapeutics*, 40(3), 329–348. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0163-7258\(89\)90053-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/0163-7258(89)90053-0)

Appendix

Table 1. FDA-Approved Anti-HIV Drugs

Name	Mechanism	Approved Year
zidovudine (AZT, ZDV)	NRTI	1987
lamivudine (3TC) Epivir	NRTI	1995
abacavir (ABC) Ziagen	NRTI	1998
tenofovir disoproxil fumarate (TDF) Viread	NRTI	2001
emtricitabine (FTC) Emtriva	NRTI	2003
tenofovir alafenamide (TAF)	NRTI	2016
nevirapine (NVP) Viramune	NNRTI	1996
efavirenz (EFV) Sustiva	NNRTI	1998
etravirine (ETR) Intelence	NNRTI	2008
rilpivirine (RPV) Edurant	NNRTI	2011
doravirine (DOR) Pifeltro	NNRTI	2018
saquinavir (SQV) Invirase	PI	1995
ritonavir (RTV) Norvir	PI	1996
lopinavir (LPV)	PI	2000
atazanavir (ATV) Reyataz	PI	2003
fosmaprenavir (FOS-APV) Lexiva	PI	2003
tipranavir (TPV) Aptivus	PI	2005
darunavir (DRV) Prezista	PI	2006
raltegravir (RAL) Isentress	INSTI	2007
elvitegravir (EVG)	INSTI	2012
dolutegravir (DTG) Tivicay	INSTI	2013
bictegravir (BIC)	INSTI	2018
3TC/AZT Combivir	Combination drugs	1997
LPV/RTV (LPVr) Kaletra	Combination drugs	2000
ABC/3TC/AZT Trizivir	Combination drugs	2000
FTC/TDF Truvada	Combination drugs	2004
ABC/3TC Epzicom	Combination drugs	2004
EFV/FTC/TDF Atripla	Combination drugs	2006
FTC/RPV/TDF Complera	Combination drugs	2011
EVG/cobisistat (COBI) /FTC/TDF Stribild	Combination drugs	2012
ABC/DTG/3TC Trimeq	Combination drugs	2014
ABC/DTG/3TC Trimeq	Combination drugs	2015
DRV/COBI Prezcofix	Combination drugs	2015
EVG/COBI/FTC/TAF Genvoya	Combination drugs	2015
FTC/RPV/TAF Odefsey	Combination drugs	2016
FTC/TAF Descovy	Combination drugs	2016
DTG/RPV Juluca	Combination drugs	2017
EFV/3TC/TDF Symfi	Combination drugs	2018
BIC/FTC/TAF Biktarvy	Combination drugs	2018
3TC/TDF Cimduo	Combination drugs	2018
DOR/3TC/TDF Delstrigo	Combination drugs	2018

